

BOOK REVIEW

Pipe dreams. Water and empire in Central Asia's Aral Sea basin

by Maya K. Peterson, Cambridge, United Kingdom, Cambridge University Press, 2019, 416 pp., \$120.00 (hardback), ISBN: 9781108475471; \$30.00 (paperback), ISBN: 9781108468541, \$26.00 (eBook), ISBN: 9781108675055; <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108673075>

Reviewed by Madina Gazieva

Scholarly prophecies of imminent water wars plagued Central Asia ever since its nations gained independence from the Soviet Union. Considering the growing frequency of climate crisis-induced droughts around the world, this is a particularly good time to revisit the environmental histories which brought us here, and Maya K. Peterson's *Pipe Dreams* could not be more timely. Shortlisted for the Central Eurasian Studies Society's 2020 Book Award in History and the Humanities, the tome chronicles Tsarist and Bolshevik manipulation of land, water and society to fulfil their visions of a cotton monoculture in Central Asia's Aral Sea Basin. Across both regimes, such colonial aspirations were justified by global "irrigation age" (14) narratives of modernity, technology, and man's conquest over nature. Drawing on a wide range of archival material from Central Asia, Russia and the US, *Pipe Dreams* offers an original and authoritative account of the early events leading up to the tragic desiccation of the Aral Sea, and is indispensable to anyone seeking to understand the roots of the region's current environmental challenges.

The book uses an environmental history approach to unravel the processes of subjugation and empire-building surrounding hydraulic projects in Central Asia under tsarist Russia and the early Soviet Union. Peterson's nuanced analysis reveals continuity in the regimes' aspiration of bringing civilisation through irrigation, but change in the scale and modality of achieving these ends. Whereas under Tsarist Russia the novelty of the landscape and atomised nature of the

governing elite resulted in a hybrid indigenous-Russian water governance with limited results, the centralisation and mass-scale mobilisation of forced, manual labour which characterised the Soviet modality, culminated in the full-fledged irrigation of Central Asia so desired by Tsarist administrators. Despite these differences, in both regimes, the discourse of modernisation and civilisation served to legitimate their varied strategies of exploitation and rule internally and globally.

The book is divided temporally into two sections, finishing with an epilogue and conclusion. The first four chapters cover Tsarist irrigation projects and rule across Central Asia, and the last two - the early Soviet regime leading up to WWII.

Chapter 1, *The Land beyond the Rivers*, begins with the mystical appearance of a Russian vessel in the Aral Sea in 1848. This marked the beginning of Russia's encounter with Central Asia's silt-laden, "vagabond rivers" – the Syr Darya and the Amu Darya, whose control was "closely tied to the imperial imagination to the control of its peoples" (32). Disgruntled by the defeat in the Crimean War, which, along with the US Civil War, contributed to a global "cotton famine" (38), Russia oriented its imperial ambitions towards the east, invading the Ferghana Valley and the Khanate of Khiva and annexing the Emirate of Bukhara in the 1860s and 1870s, forming the Tsarist Governor-Generalship of Turkestan. The irrigation of the Aral Sea Basin for lucrative cotton production via European scientific methods was swiftly made the priority of imperial ambitions. However, attempts to impose a Western scientific model conflicted with existing Sharia-based, customary water use arrangements, which the chapter explores in detail. Obligated to concede to local or hybrid water management practices, the Tsarist regime nonetheless persisted in its attempts to irrigate the region to boost its international prestige and return Turkestan to its glorious past.

Chapter 2, *Eastern Eden* details the canal-building ventures of the exiled Grand Duke Nikolai Konstantinovich, who was granted autonomy over irrigation in the Hungry Steppe in the late 1800s. Spurred by the romanticism of the irrigation age, the eccentric and ambitious Grand

Duke “felt that irrigation was the perfect arena in which to demonstrate the benefits of Russian rule over Turkestan” (77). By promoting local leaders and customary irrigation practices of indigenous Central Asians, and offering wages to the canal builders, he became the self-appointed ruler of the hybrid, “Russo-Asiatic” world. The chapter additionally explores two crucial developments: the social dynamics caused by mass immigration of Russian peasants attracted by the job prospects in irrigation construction, and the invocation of Persian and Turkic tales as a tool of colonial legitimation, integral to future Soviet statecraft.

The legitimacy of customary irrigation practices was short-lived, and as explored in Chapter 3, *To Create a New Turkestan*, the colonial administration, with limited success, became determined to bring order to what was perceived a less efficient system of water management. These efforts were intensified in the light of the fervent policy of cotton monoculture, propelled by the panic over America’s monopoly over cotton. In the territory of modern-day Uzbekistan, cotton was cultivated at the expense of the cash crop rice, a staple for the indigenous population and more suited to salinized soil. Their needs, however, were deemed secondary “to those of the newly arrived Slavic settlers who ate mostly wheat, barley and rye” (159). Already in the early 1900s, observers warned of the dangers cotton monoculture which were ignored by the Tsarist administration. Instead, to avoid food shortages and free up more space for cotton, the Russian government developed an ambitious plan to designate the region of Semireche as the “‘breadbasket’ of Turkestan” (163).

Chapter 4, *The Land of Bread and Honey*, depicts the struggles Semireche’s Chu Valley Irrigation Project (modern Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan) in the early twentieth century, which illustrated “the limits to peaceful Russian colonisation of Turkestan” and spill-overs of the “cotton fever” (169). Control over and effective irrigation of the region for grain production necessitated the settlement of semi-nomadic peoples through land seizures. This led to a variety of survival strategies among the natives, where some sought to manipulate the existing laws to their advantage

while others fled to China. These struggles culminated in the violent 1916 Turkestan uprising, concentrated in the Semireche, against a Tsarist government weakened by the Great War.

The final two chapters are set in the early Soviet period. Chapter 5, *Sundering the Chains of Nature*, discusses the 1920s attempts to overhaul Tsarist-era, “outdated”, native irrigation practices, with European “engineered” systems which were to emancipate the people of Turkestan from the shackles of nature, capitalism and colonialism. Nationalisation, centralisation and bureaucratisation, coupled with land and water reforms to sedentarise nomadic people, enacted under the New Economic Policy, served to expand cotton production. In reality, by the late 1920s, very few irrigation systems were “engineered”, partly due to the dearth of qualified hydraulic specialists and resilience of customary practices. As famine spread across the USSR, in efforts to distract from the shortcomings of Stalinist planning and ensure the perception of success, the Soviet regime launched a campaign against Tsarist-era “bourgeois specialists”, deemed disloyal to Bolshevik visions of an emancipated Turkestan. The overemphasis on cotton cultivation, however, further deprived Central Asians of vital food sources and prolonged the collectivisation-induced famine.

Chapter 6, *From Shockwork to People’s Construction*, focuses on the 1930s irrigation of Tajikistan’s Vakhsh Valley, which was to “at last embody the promises of the revolution and, [...] put Soviet modernity on display for not only the peoples of the Soviet Union, but for the peoples of the ‘East’ who lived just beyond Soviet borders” (268). In collaboration with American engineers, the Vakhsh Valley was to be transformed into a “cotton garden” (288) through new forms of Soviet labour and imported machinery. The harshness and remoteness of the landscape, however, made recruitment and retainment of workers difficult, while imported machinery rarely made it to the campsite. Instead, masses of collective farm workers and political prisoners were forcefully mobilised and resettled into the Vakhsh Valley to perform manual labour. The Soviet state, celebrated “people’s labour” as a victory over machines, which served as a testament to the

superiority of Soviet fervour and commitment to revolution, a familiar tactic frequently mobilised for decades to come.

The Epilogue outlines the consolidation of the Soviet regime and continuing “war on nature” (321) through dams and river diversions for cotton monoculture, which culminated in the tragic desiccation of the Aral Sea and its dire effects on health and livelihoods. The legacies of the historic agricultural policies shape the region to this day, where cotton remains highly strategic, and water – contested.

Through the unique, interdisciplinary perspective of environmental history, *Pipe Dreams* fuses the themes of modernisation, environmental and agricultural policy and state-building, which shape the social and political realities of modern-day Central Asia. This lens also allows Peterson to confidently qualify pre-WWII Soviet Central Asia as a colony, due to its designation and exploitation as a source of raw materials for the Soviet state. Peterson thus aligns with Adeeb Khalid and Botakoz Kassymbekova by interrogating the role of coercive modalities of Soviet state-building, contributing to the ongoing conversation on the specifics of the current, post-colonial condition of Central Asia.

Indeed, in her conclusion, Peterson directly responds to Sven Beckert’s *Empire of Cotton*, on the role of cotton in the global capitalist economy, noting:

“it seems particularly tragic, then, that with all of their inventiveness and revolutionary spirit, the creators of the world’s first socialist state could come up with no other vision for Central Asia than continuing to develop the region into that global symbol of slavery and capitalist oppression, a cotton plantation” (335).

Such a perspective links Tsarist and Soviet Central Asia with the global literature on roles of slavery, colonialism and empire in the development of modern capitalism. This claim, and the ideological paradox it represents, could have been enhanced by a more thorough elaboration of the value of the region’s cotton within the Soviet and international trade networks. Nonetheless, Peterson’s opus,

the centrepiece of her short but influential career, is an engaging and powerful account of the coercive transformation of Central Asia's social and environmental landscape, and an essential contribution to the budding field of human-environment relations.

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